

Stocktake and Lessons Learnt from the Ecosystem-Based Adaptation to Climate Change Project in Seychelles

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1. Introduction

The most recent report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) indicated that the earth's average temperature could increase by up to 5.4°C by 2100 under the business-as-usual scenario (IPCC, 2022). Such an increase will amplify already existing vulnerabilities, especially for nations that are highly dependent on livelihood activities such as fisheries, agriculture and tourism, which are climate-sensitive (Etongo, 2021; Wheeler and Von Braun, 2013). While changes in climatic conditions will exacerbate water stress, variability in rainfall patterns will also affect the availability of water, especially as access to water for domestic, agricultural and industrial uses continues to face intense competition (Olmstead, 2014; Arnell et al., 2011). This could result in declining agricultural productivity with a ripple effect on food and nutrition security while concomitantly inducing other climate-related risks, such as the prevalence of invasive alien plant species and flooding events from sea-level rise (Scarano, 2017). These challenges, if unabated, have the potential to constrain sustainable development especially among Small Island Developing States (SIDS) that suffer from common environmental problems due to their smallness, remoteness and exposure to natural hazards (Scandurra et al., 2018).

To address the impacts of climate change, international development agencies promote the use of ecosystem-based adaptation (EbA) to mitigate the effects of climate change on ecosystems and societies while providing multiple benefits in terms of goods and services (Reid et al., 2019). In addition, EbA is often more cost-effective than alternative adaptation options involving hard infrastructure. For example, restoration of mangroves to reduce coastal erosion is, in many cases, more cost-effective than constructing seawalls (Munang et al., 2013; Newsham et al., 2018). What then is EbA? According to the Convention on Biological Diversity (CBD), EbA is defined as: *'the use of biodiversity and ecosystem services as part of an overall adaptation strategy to help people to adapt to the adverse effects of climate change'* (CBD, 2009). This adaptation strategy is now promoted as one of the nature-based solutions (NbS) to address climate change. NbS is an umbrella concept for ecosystem-related approaches and is defined by the International Union for the Conservation of Nature (IUCN) as: *'actions to protect, sustainably manage and restore natural or modified ecosystems that address*

societal challenges effectively and adaptively, simultaneously providing human well-being and biodiversity benefits' (Cohen-Shacham et al., 2016).

EbA can be implemented in multiple different ways and is applicable to a range of ecosystems across a diversity of geographical scales. Some examples of EbA interventions implemented globally include mangrove restoration for protection from storm surges, catchment management to mitigate against droughts and flash floods, rangeland management to prevent desertification, and forest rehabilitation through tree planting (Mills et al., 2020; Chong, 2014). The scale of EbA projects can vary from small, individual family, multi-use home gardens of a few hundred square meters (Harvey et al., 2017), to large-scale rehabilitation or restoration projects covering a much larger area (Mills et al., 2015; Reid et al., 2019). Site-specific issues, institutional arrangements, governance frameworks and human, financial and material resources are important for the effective implementation of EbA projects. More important is the establishment of a monitoring and evaluation team to ensure the sustainability of EbA investments beyond the project life cycle. As such, challenges and lessons learnt are important to guide future implementation in Seychelles and elsewhere. Therefore, this paper provides a comprehensive stocktake of success stories pertaining to the 'EbA to Climate Change in Seychelles' project, also known as the 'EbA Project', and is based on extensive consultation with relevant stakeholders who participated in the project implementation. Challenges encountered and recommendations to ensure the sustainability of the project are also provided.

Between 2013 and 2019, the *Enhancing Capacity, Knowledge and Technology Support to Build Climate Resilience of Vulnerable Developing Countries* project, referred to as the 'EbA South Project', also occurred in Seychelles (Mills et al., 2020). This project was developed through a collaboration between the China National Development and Reform Commission, the United Nations Environment Programme and the Government of Seychelles. Some of the EbA South Project interventions were similar to the EbA Project discussed in this paper. For example, mangrove restoration features prominently in both projects as an EbA intervention to provide climate change mitigation and adaptation co-benefits.

2. The EbA Adaptation Fund Project Seychelles

The 'EbA Project' was launched in 2014 and officially ended in March 2022. Funding for this project was provided by the Adaptation Fund (AF) through the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP). The Ministry of Agriculture, Climate Change and Environment (MACCE) in collaboration with the GoS-UNDP-GEF Programme Coordination Unit (PCU) were responsible for its implementation. The PCU is a local management system of the Global Environment Facility (GEF) and the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) in

Seychelles that ensures the effective coordination and implementation of UNDP-GEF funded projects implemented by the Government of Seychelles (GoS) through the MACCE. The overall objective of the EbA Project was to reduce the vulnerability of Seychelles to climate change by addressing issues of water scarcity and flooding.

Climate change projections for Seychelles have shown that while rainfall in general will increase, its future pattern will become even more variable (GoS, 2009). Much of the precipitation is falling in sharp bursts, creating heavy flooding in the wet season, while extended periods of drought occur during the dry season (GoS, 2009). As the country does not have a large water-storage capacity, and the topography of the islands constrains such infrastructure, water supplies are heavily dependent on rainfall. This has led to competition for water between domestic and agricultural uses, which is now an issue of major concern. This is because agriculture in Seychelles is highly dependent on irrigation, and livestock farming uses a lot of water in the production process. Therefore, farmers who depend on the Public Utilities Corporation (PUC) for water pay higher prices when compared to those utilizing water from irrigation schemes where a flat rate is paid irrespective of consumption. As such, the EbA Project sought to restore the ecosystem functionality and resilience of watersheds and coastal processes to secure ecosystem services such as critical water provisioning and flood attenuation.

The EbA Project developed and implemented EbA through a landscape and watershed strategy that builds upon Seychelles' existing biodiversity conservation programmes in relation to the rehabilitation and restoration of ecosystem functions that support water supply and flood control services. This paper presents a compilation of stakeholder success stories, challenges and lessons learnt throughout the eight EbA Projects.

3. Implemented EbA interventions

The activities implemented within the framework of the EbA Project are grouped into six categories as follows: i) rehabilitation of degraded wetlands; ii) mangrove restoration; iii) river management; iv) tree planting; v) science component; and vi) monitoring and evaluation. Each of these components are presented in detail in their respective sub sections below.

3.1. Rehabilitation of degraded wetlands

Wetlands in Seychelles are threatened by a number of natural (e.g. storm surges), biological (e.g. invasive alien species) and anthropogenic factors (e.g. pollution, land reclamation, infrastructure development) leading to intense degradation and significant losses (GoS, 2019). To address this degradation, the EbA Project carried out rehabilitation works at wetlands in

the Baie Lazare and Anse Royale districts. The rehabilitation works were implemented across four sites in Baie Lazare and one site in Anse Royale.

3.1.1. Wetland rehabilitation at Baie Lazare

Prior to the EbA interventions at one of the sites in Baie Lazare, known as Bougainville, the wetland was completely degraded. There was no sign of water and the wetland was dominated by invasive alien species (e.g. *Merremia peltata*) and used for waste disposal (Figure 1).

Figure 1: Status of the wetland at Dan Sours wetland in Bougainville, Baie Lazare as of 2014 prior to rehabilitation activities

(Photo Credit: Johan Mendez)

The EbA project team engaged the local community in this area and presented the rehabilitation activities. Given the greenery at the site, community members believed this site was in good condition and did not see the need for any intervention. They were skeptical about the possibility of water returning to this site as the proposed intervention was a first of its kind in Seychelles. Activities at this site began in 2014 through the engagement of local contractors and community participation. These activities included the eradication of invasive plant species, dredging of the site and the planting of native wetland plant species (Figure 2). Significant progress was recorded within a period of three years, from a degraded wetland in 2014 (Figure 1), to a functional wetland ecosystem in 2017 (Figure 2).

After

Figure 2: Status of the rehabilitated wetland at Dan Sours wetland in Bougainville, Baie Lazare as of 2017
(Photo Credit: Johan Mendez)

To increase the water-retention capacity of the wetland, a locally designed gabion wall was constructed in 2018, also with active community participation (Figure 3). The amount of water stored has increased and the farmers in this community use the water to irrigate their crops. Agriculture in Seychelles is highly dependent on irrigation due to the low water-retention capacity of the soil. Therefore, water from wetlands and rivers, if managed properly, has the potential to ensure access to water for irrigation, food security and livelihoods under a changing climate. The rehabilitated wetland at Bougainville now features a thriving forest of endemic palms, an all-around trail, bridges, park benches, and litter bins (Figure 3). It has become a site of attraction used for picnic, educational purposes and ecotourism.

Figure 3: Construction of a locally-designed gabion to enhance water retention at the Dan Sours wetland in Bougainville, Baie Lazare.
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

3.1.2. Wetland rehabilitation at Anse Royale

The site at Anse Royale wetland is connected to the sea via the Anse Royale River which flows between the University of Seychelles and adjacent crop land. This site was also covered with invasive alien plant species and served as a dumping area for household waste. Invasive species were removed from the site and the silt that had accumulated was excavated to widen the channel of the wetland (Figure 4). Local contractors had to design wooden platforms to avoid the excavators from sinking into the mud. The wetland became more visible after the dredging when compared to the situation prior to the intervention (Figure 5) and tidal waters can now flow in and out of the wetland without constriction.

Figure 4: Excavation of wetland at Anse Royale in 2018 to remove accumulated sediment and invasive species
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

Before

After

Figure 5: Restoration of degraded wetland at Anse Royale before (2015) and after (2018)
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

3.2. Mangrove restoration

Mangrove restoration activities by the EbA Project were implemented across three sites on Mahè Island as follows: Anse Royale, Northeast Point and Caiman River in the Anse Boileau districts. Seychelles has lost approximately 70% of its original mangrove cover and restoration activities are important to enhance its buffering potential from sea level rise. This section on mangrove restoration focuses on issues related to zonation, raising a nursery, site preparation and planting pattern. For more detail on this topic, see Etongo and Vel (2021).

3.2.1. Zonation

Mangrove forests often exhibit zonation patterns due to intertidal gradients along the coastline. It is important to understand the zonation of mangrove species (ZMS), which often contributes to the responses of individual species to variations in different abiotic and biotic factors (Bullock et al., 2017). Some mangrove species tolerate longer durations of tidal inundation than others, while some have a relatively higher tolerance for salinity (Lewis, 2006). Furthermore, different parameters must be accounted for in a zone in which a certain species occurs. These parameters include depth, duration and frequency of tidal inundation, soil salinity, as well as the amount of freshwater available. Thus, according to Hogarth (2015), mangroves are not distributed randomly but are established at specific sites with suitable abiotic and biotic conditions that are optimal for each species.

Site visits in 2015 and drone imagery taken in 2017 formed a baseline survey of mangrove zonation to delineate the different mangrove species (Delpont and Berry, 2017) at the Anse Royale site (Figure 6). Based on the zonation pattern that was established, each of the corresponding mangrove species at Anse Royale were identified as follows: 4331.8m² for *Avicennia marina*, 12579.8m² for *Rizophora mucronata*, 60.1m² for *Bruguiera gymnorhiza*, and 348.4m² for both *Avicennia marina* and *Rizophora mucronata* (Figure 6) (Delpont and Berry, 2017).

Zonation of mangrove species in Anse Royale visualized on an aerial orthomosaic done by drone

Figure 6: Zonation of mangrove species to identify area coverage and specific locations prior to restoration at the Anse Royale site
(Photo Credit: Christophe Delpont)

3.2.2. Raising a nursery

To ensure the mangroves have a greater chance of survival once planted, and thrive at this site, the EbA Project nursery raised mangrove seedlings under different conditions through an experimental design by the University of Seychelles. *Avicennia marina*, *Rhizophora mucronata* and *Ceriops tagal* were subjected to freshwater and seawater treatments (Figure 7). Mangrove seedlings irrigated using freshwater in the nursery, such as *A. marina*, were found to be less affected by freshwater when planted, and displayed higher growth rates as a result (Etongo et al., 2022). This was a pre-trial experiment for mangrove propagation in fresh and seawater with important lessons that can guide future restoration activities in Seychelles. For more information regarding this experiment, see Etongo et al. (2022).

Figure 7: Mangrove nursery in shade house (7A) and in the wetland (7B) at the Anse Royale site
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

3.2.3. Site preparation

The fast-growing, invasive plant species presented a major challenge even after clearing at the Anse Royale site. With the active participation of members of the Mont Plaisir watershed committee, the EbA Project was able to install mesh mat at the site to control the growth and spread of invasive species such as *Merremia peltata* (Figure 8). The role of local knowledge in the control of invasive plant species is well demonstrated here and will prove useful when applied in future restoration works. The Anse Royale site is now covered with the native plant, *Ipomoea pes-caprae*, commonly known as morning glory. This species has creeping root stems that form dense patches that anchor sand and produce humus which is important for the wetland ecosystem.

Figure 8: Installation of mesh mat to control the proliferation of invasive alien species at the Anse Royale mangrove restoration site

(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

Coconut trees and their seedlings were also common at the Anse Royale site and were removed from the wetland (Figure 9). Coconut trees have a long-term impact on the sustainability of wetlands due to their sand trapping abilities, and had trapped huge quantities of sand in the Anse Royale wetland, shrinking its size and obstructing the flow of water.

Figure 9: Removal of coconut from the wetland prior to planting of mangrove seedlings
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

3.2.4. Planting of mangroves

There are three planting patterns commonly used to plant mangroves with each of them having certain advantages. These planting patterns include strip, inverted v-shape, and cluster planting (Etongo and Vel, 2021). Strip planting is applicable for most conditions, however, consideration needs to be given to decreasing the spacing between seedlings at sites that experience medium to high waves. The strip planting pattern was adopted at the Anse Royale site with a spacing of 1 to 1.5 m apart (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Mangrove seedlings planted using the strip pattern at the Anse Royale site, Mahe Island
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

Propagules of mangroves such as *Rhizophora mucronata*, *Xylocarpus granatum* were also planted directly into the ground at Anse Royale wetland with very close spacings (Figure 11). This method is cheaper and easier than propagation in a nursery but can easily fail if planting occurs during high tides. Observations over time at the Anse Royale site showed that these propagules easily adapted to the conditions and grew normally.

Figure 11: Planting of mangrove propagules by Advanced Level Students at the Anse Royale site in 2018
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

3.3. River management

Undisturbed natural vegetation can provide ground cover and soil holding capacity and, by minimizing soil and water runoff, protect against erosion. This in turn maintains soil fertility, regulates downstream water flow, decreases the risk of flooding, and maintains low silt and sediment loads in water courses while concomitantly providing protection for the terrestrial and marine environment (Fleischmann, 2019). Deforestation and heavy rains leading to flooding are the cause of riverbank erosion in Seychelles. This is common among rivers in the south of Mahe and, therefore, the reinforcement of riverbanks with the active participation of community members, including farmers, was among the interventions of the EbA Project at Biae Lazare (see Figure 12). Actions taken included the use of geotextile sandbags in addition to the planting of endemic tree species that are water loving as part of the strategy for river management. Examples of such plants include *Pandanus hornei* and *Phoenicophorium borsigianum* (Thief Palm). The Thief Palm in particular grows from sea level to high altitudes, usually in damp places such as along the banks of streams and rivers (Hill and Currie, 2007).

Figure 12: Restoration of riverbanks at Biae Lazare with sandbags and native plant species
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

3.4. Tree planting on fire-ravaged forest areas

Forest fires on Praslin, a granitic island 48kms northwest of Mahè island, have degraded forest ecosystems by exposing the bare soil to the full force of erosion (Figure 13). The EbA Project team, in collaboration with the Terrestrial Restoration Action Society Seychelles (TRASS), had a target to rehabilitate 23 hectares of degraded forest areas on Praslin Island through the planting of indigenous tree species. Phase 1 of the tree planting activity occurred between 2016 and 2017 with only 5 ha of degraded forests successfully rehabilitated. This initial phase of the rehabilitation activity was a learning-by-doing stage with lots of lessons learnt that led to the successful rehabilitation of 18 ha during phase 2 of the project between 2019 and 2020 (Etongo et al., 2021). Some of the lessons learnt during the rehabilitation works include adding a kilogram of organic manure for direct seeding. The humus layer of the soil (top layer) is fast eroded (see Figure 13) and seeds need nutrients to grow. This is one of the lessons learnt that contributed towards the greater success rate in phase 2 of the rehabilitation activity.

Figure 13: Fire ravaged forest at Anse la Blague on Praslin Island which occurred in August 2020
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

A common problem that was identified during phase 1 of the rehabilitation activity was the loss of seedlings due to soil erosion induced by rainfall especially on steep slopes. As a mitigation strategy, smaller fragments of boulders were placed at right angles to the flow direction to prevent soil erosion. In addition, best practice tips were shared with community

members prior to planting of seedlings, such as the removal of polythene bags before planting, and to ensure that seedlings still have soil intact after the removal of the polythene bags. Figure 14 is a tree planting session that occurred in December 2020 with students from the Environmental Science Programme at the University of Seychelles together with community members from La Digue and Praslin Island. This activity was organized by TRASS in collaboration with the EbA Project.

Figure 14: Tree planting on degraded forest area on Praslin Island during the month of December 2020
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

3.5. Science component

The science component for this project included water quality monitoring, measuring water flow and light levels (light climate) within the forests. From January 2016, six permanent water-sampling points at Val d'Endor were regularly visited by Environmental Science students from the University of Seychelles who collected water samples for analysis (Figure 15). Such analysis provided baseline information to identify trends or changes in water quality caused by point- or nonpoint-source pollution and nutrient enrichment. Two of the six sites showed very low water quality, which was linked to point-source pollution from human activities (Fleischmann et al., 2020). Long-term monitoring is important for assessing water

quality and is recommended to occur on a monthly basis for a period of ten years to ensure gradual changes over time are captured.

Figure 15: A visit by Environmental Science students from the University of Seychelles to one of the river monitoring stations at Baie Lazare, Mahe Island
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

Monitoring stations were set up across six sites by the EbA Project to monitor water flow and stream discharge rates using the V-notch weirs that were installed at the Val d'Endor site on Mahe Island (Figure 16). A weir is an overflow dam used to alter the flow characteristics of a river or stream and it takes the form of a barrier across the river that causes water to pool behind the structure, while allowing water to flow over the top (Figure 16). According to Fleischmann et al. (2020), two of the six monitoring sites had the highest rate of water discharge, and these rivers were considered as the main water sources given that water discharge was consistent.

Figure 16: Measuring water discharge to identify streams that are important water providers
(Photo Credit: Terence Vel)

Forest light climate is another aspect that was considered due to its impact on forest rehabilitation. By understanding the appropriate forest light climate for indigenous plant species, the control of invasive plant species can be more effective. For example, *Phoenixophorium borsigianum* is considered as a high canopy specialist. Its shade tolerance and capacity to grow even at very low light levels make this palm particularly successful in competing with *Cinnamomum verum*, and other invaders in shaded forest areas (Fleischmann et al., 2020). The concept of ‘novel ecosystem management’ should be adhered to and removing plant invaders should be done in a way that does not compromise their present ecological function (Virapongse et al., 2016). Therefore, Fleischmann et al. (2020) recommended that tree felling should only be performed where the rejuvenation of native trees has been achieved; for example, in areas where natural rejuvenation of native palms has occurred, or where seedlings have been planted. Another recommendation is that the workforce undertaking forest rehabilitation should create as few gaps in the forest canopy as possible so as not to benefit invasive plants by increasing light penetration. Suppressing invasive plant growth in this way allows more time to be spent on establishing seedlings and saplings than removing invasive trees.

4. Monitoring and evaluation

EbA interventions operate within socio-ecological systems that are exposed to disturbances which in some cases could lead to unintended outcomes (Virapongse et al., 2016). This reaffirms the need for constant monitoring and evaluation, which was considered an integral component in the EbA Project. For example, the access track into the wetland rehabilitation site at Dan Sours became eroded towards the end of 2019 (Figure 17). The entrance is a little steep, and the driving of cars in and out eroded the soil that was further washed into the wetland after rainfall. As a response strategy, a common erosion control method that has proven to be effective in Seychelles was implemented through the installation of a nylon fishing net at the affected site (Figure 17). The nylon fishing nets are provided free of charge by the Indian Ocean Tuna Limited (IOT) company in Seychelles.

Figure 17: Nylon fishing net used for erosion control at the Dan Sours wetland rehabilitation site in Bougainville, Mahe Island
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

Another problem observed while the EbA Project was ongoing was that of an algal bloom at one of the sites in Baie Lazare (Figure 18). The major source of pollution at this site was from a pig farm's waste water being discharged into the wetland. Although the outlet of the wetland has been widened to enhance the flow of water, site selection for different agricultural practices should consider a landscape approach. For example, pig farms should be located at sites that will have little or no impact on wetlands. This is because livestock farming,

especially piggeries, are highly dependent on good quality water for animal production. Therefore, wetlands and rivers that are necessary to support agriculture should not be polluted by other farming types that are also highly dependent on water.

Figure 18: Signs of an alga bloom at one of the wetland rehabilitation sites in Baie Lazare
(Photo Credit: Daniel Etongo)

5. The way forward

The EbA Project recorded several success stories that are providing multiple benefits for local livelihoods and the environment. Some of the success stories, as already mentioned, include water security through the rehabilitation of wetlands, local ecotourism, food security, civil protection, mangrove restoration, revitalization of community engagement through the creation of watershed committees, among others. Given that the EbA Project officially ended in March 2022, there is a need to ensure that the benefits from this project in terms of ecosystem goods and services are sustained over time. As such, through extensive consultation with EbA Project team members, this article has provided a number of recommendations as a way forward.

Although the watershed committees will undertake tree planting and the cleaning of trash from these sites, the role of local contractors for regular maintenance of these sites will more effectively ensure the provisioning of ecosystem goods and services. For example, aquatic plants are fast growing and, without regular control, they will compromise the long-term

sustainability of the wetlands. It was suggested that local contractors should be hired once every three months to maintain the wetlands. The contractors and their activity could be funded by the water levy paid by the PUC to the Environment Trust Fund. Since these aquatic plants filter the water and also absorb nutrients, a win-win approach would be to convert the water weeds to compost to be used by farmers. Compost enriches the soil, helps to retain moisture, and reduces the need for chemical fertilizers. Furthermore, a comprehensive land-use plan is needed by the Department of Agriculture to guide the allocation of agricultural lands going forward. For example, plots of land above the water catchment area should be allocated for agroforestry and not for livestock farming.

A key question that was raised by some of the stakeholders is ‘what will happen now that the project has ended?’ This is an important question that has implications at different levels. Five watershed committees have been created with one on Praslin and four on Mahè. With financial support from the EbA Project, the Baie Lazare Watershed Management Plan 2022-2026 was completed in February 2022. While this document has a comprehensive action plan and cost estimates for 17 activities, it falls short of an annual implementation timeline or funders for these activities. According to the plan, the main source of income will be donations from local businesses and individuals in the community. As a recommendation, key stakeholders such as Seychelles Breweries (Seybrew) and water bottling companies should be approached by these committees for financial support.

The ongoing Ridge-to-Reef Project has been mentioned in the watershed management plan as one of the key actors. This is important given that material, technical and financial support will be provided for some of the action plans, thereby serving as an ‘add-on’ to the EbA Project activities. The Ridge-to-Reef Project has provided training on watershed management to key stakeholders and is planning another training activity on forest management. Such training activities will equip stakeholders with the knowledge and skills needed to manage the wetlands and ensure their sustainability over time.

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Johan Mendez is an hydrogeologist working in water cycle restoration for small islands since 2006, and has had the opportunity to learn from various in-depth experiential expertise along the way, working on various projects in Europe and in the Western Indian Ocean region, specializing in watershed hydrological function restoration through landscape's ecosystem regeneration. He previously obtained two Master Degrees; one from Paris-XI University in Geology and Environment and one from the University of Quebec at Rimouski (UQAR), in Marine Resources Management. Blending a unique combination of systems thinking and awareness, Johan implemented water resilience objectives of the Ecosystem-Based Adaptation to Climate Change (EBA) Project in Seychelles from its inception in 2014 until the end of the project in March 2022 by providing an action-oriented process to improve communities' relationship with their landscape, through enhancing water storage and the ecosystems in which they reside. An ecological approach to systems design remains the core of his philosophy on water resources management. Harvesting time and the productivity of natural systems is the guiding principle. Dedicated to planting our ancestors' wisdom back in the ground so that future generations are able to enjoy Mother Earth as we have been able to, Johan now works all over the world helping agrarians by providing solutions and field training to restore natural flows on their land, increasing water for crops and livestock, but also for wildlife and downstream water users. And a restored water cycle means cooler ground temperature and natural heat dissipation, which, if implemented at scale, can have a major impact on global warming mitigation.